

THE GIANT RADIO ARRAY FOR NEUTRINO DETECTION (GRAND): STATUS AND PROSPECTS

Rafael Alves Batista

on behalf of the GRAND Collaboration

Sorbonne Université

Institut d'Astrophysique de Paris (IAP)

Lab. Physique Nucléaire et des Hautes Énergies (LPNHE)

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✉ rafael.alves_batista@iap.fr

🏠 www.8rafael.com

HORIZONAntenna

GRAND Collaboration. Comp. Phys. Comms. 308 (2025) 109461. arXiv:2408.10926

expected performance

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Guépin, Kotera, Oikonomou. Nat. Rev. Phys. 4 (2022) 697. arXiv:2207.12205

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 - ◆ for 1000 BNS mergers (1 month): < 10 GeV cm^{-2}

prototypes layout

backgrounds

Errico, de Mello Mello Neto, Timmermans for the GRAND Collaboration.
 PoS (ICRC2025) 1024. arXiv:2507.07407

- ▶ CR event with energy ~ 13.9 EeV
- ▶ comparison with Auger
 - ◆ directional reconstruction: good agreement
 - ◆ time offset: ~ 10 μ s

Kato, Prévotat, Alves Batista for the GRAND Collaboration.
 PoS (ICRC2025) 298. arXiv:2508.01306

- ▶ **GRAND concept**
 - ◆ diffuse sensitivity of $\sim 10^{-10} \text{ GeV cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$
 - ◆ baseline design: ~ 20 sub-arrays of 10k antennas
 - ◆ exploring related concepts (e.g., HERON)
- ▶ **autonomous detection** (*self-trigger*) principle validated
- ▶ GP300 will be completed by the end of 2027
 - ◆ CR physics at $\sim 10 \text{ PeV} - 1 \text{ EeV}$
 - ◆ transition between galactic and extragalactic CRs
 - ◆ optimisation of reconstruction tools for neutrino searches
- ▶ around $\sim 2030-2035$
 - ◆ **GRAND10k**: first neutrino-capable array
 - ◆ UHE neutrino astronomy

exploring other strategies: **the HERON concept**

- ▶ **HERON:** Hybrid Elevated Radio Observatory for Neutrinos
- ▶ phased arrays → better trigger + lower energy threshold
- ▶ standalone antennas → better reconstruction

Kotera et al. for the BEACON and GRAND Collaborations.
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back-up slides

<https://github.com/grand-mother/grand>

- ▶ python package for analysing GRAND data
- ▶ handles coordinate systems and topography
- ▶ detailed implementation of geomagnetic field
- ▶ includes Galactic noise
- ▶ encompass all RF-chain parameters
- ▶ contains tools to store and manage data in standard format

Kato, Prévotat, Alves Batista for the GRAND Collaboration.
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- ▶ **1.** signal input and filter chain, with 4 inputs
- ▶ **2.** analog-to-digital chip (ADC)
 - ◆ 500 MS/s, 14 bits
- ▶ **3.** system on chip: field-programmable gate array (FPGA) and central processing unit (CPU)
- ▶ **4.** global positioning system (GPS) chip and connector
- ▶ **5.** ethernet chip
- ▶ **6.** clock
- ▶ **7.** power supply for the digital part of the board
- ▶ **8.** power supply for the analog part of the board
- ▶ **9.** power connector and switch

GRANDProto300 LNA

GRAND@Auger LNA

- ▶ **short transients:** highest detection potential
 - ◆ high-luminosity, rare, distant transients (GRBs)

- ▶ **long transients:** highest detection potential
 - ◆ local sources such as pulsars and magnetars

